

DEVELOPMENT OF THE LEGAL BASIS OF THE ACTIVITY OF CRIME PREVENTION SERVICES OF THE INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES (1999-2016)

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Abstract: The article discusses the development of the legal basis of crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, offers and recommendations for more effective organization of this activity.

Key words: Internal affairs bodies, crime prevention services, crime prevention activities, legal basis.

In our country, a unique legal system has been established to protect human rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests, as well as the property of individuals and legal entities from various offenses. This system aims to maintain public order, ensure public safety, uphold the rule of law, safeguard the security of individuals, society, and the state, and implement crime prevention measures. Within this system, the crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies play a crucial role.

It can be said that just as each participant in administrative and legal relations in society's social life has its own legal status, the crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies also have their distinct legal status.

In some sources, the concept of "legal status" is defined as the state of a subject determined by legal norms, a set of his rights and obligations.[1]

M.Z. Ziyodullaev notes that when discussing the legal status of a legal entity, along with its rights and obligations, it is possible to include its main functions.[2]

In our view, the "rights and obligations of the subject" within the concept of "legal status" mentioned above also encompass "the functions of the subject." In other words, the rights and obligations assigned to the subject by normative legal acts inherently include its tasks and functions.

Regarding the development of the legal status of crime prevention services within internal affairs bodies, which began in 2017 and is currently being consistently and comprehensively implemented as part of the New Uzbekistan reforms, it is no exaggeration to say that over the years, the normative legal acts defining the legal status of this service, an integral part of the state body, have been uniquely improved in accordance with the development of our society's social life.

In particular, looking back at history, extensive work has been carried out to improve not only the crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies but also the entire system of internal affairs. This work continues consistently to ensure peace and tranquility, public order, and public safety more effectively in our country.

Specifically, the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Concept of Maintaining Public Order and Ensuring Security in the City of Tashkent" dated April 12, 1999, can be considered the beginning of reforms in this area during the period we are discussing. The significance of these reforms lies in their comprehensive nature, covering

the entire internal affairs system and focusing on all important areas of activity. In particular, this decree reorganized the structure of the Main Department of Internal Affairs of Tashkent city, established the activities of the Patrol and Post Service and the Traffic Police on an entirely new basis, and instituted the Preventive Inspectors system based on the former police precinct inspectors.[4]

Also, based on this decision, support points were established in all 444 makhallas of the city of Tashkent, and about 1200 prevention inspectors were established in them. The results of these reforms made it possible to radically revise and strengthen work to prevent offenses, identify and eliminate the causes of crimes and the conditions that contributed to them, and ensure a significant improvement in the criminal situation in our country.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-2822 of March 27, 2001, "On Measures to Improve the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan" also has special significance in improving the legal status of crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies. This Decree defines the organizational structure and main tasks of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 6, 2001, "On Measures to Strengthen the Role of the Preventive Service in Combating Crime," adopted to ensure the implementation of this Decree, also played an important role in strengthening the legal status of the Ministry of Internal Affairs' crime prevention services. In particular, based on the aforementioned normative legal acts, support points have been established in all makhallas of the country, which are considered the lowest level of crime prevention services, the activities of prevention inspectors have been established in them, and the cooperation of the crime prevention services of the internal affairs bodies with citizens' self-government bodies and the general public, in other words, with civil society institutions, in the prevention of offenses has been further strengthened.

Furthermore, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 162 "On Measures to Improve the Infrastructure of Military Support Points" of May 16, 2002, and the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-3264 "On Measures to Further Improve the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan" of July 19, 2004, and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 442/69 "On Measures to Improve the Training of The reason is that these normative legal acts effectively influenced the formation of a completely new system of crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies, the further strengthening of their activities and further strengthening of their legal foundations and legal status, the improvement of their material and technical base and the training, retraining and advanced training of qualified personnel directly for this service in educational institutions of internal affairs bodies, the establishment of newly created structural structures in the system of crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies, that is, the activities of the base points of the internal affairs bodies and

The adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Offenses" on May 14, 2014, also serves to increase the effectiveness of work in this area and raise it to a qualitatively new level.

In particular, this law provides appropriate definitions of such basic concepts as offenses, victims of offenses, persons prone to committing offenses, antisocial behavior, social rehabilitation and social adaptation, as well as crime prevention, defines the main tasks of

crime prevention and the main principles of crime prevention and identifies general, special, individual and victimological crime prevention as types of crime prevention. These main tasks, principles, and types of crime prevention serve as a program for the effective implementation of the activities of the crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies.

At the same time, this law separately defines the bodies and institutions that carry out and participate in the prevention of offenses, their powers, and in the system of bodies and institutions that directly carry out the prevention of offenses, internal affairs bodies are also noted, and in the field of prevention of offenses, internal affairs bodies:

- participate in the development and implementation of state programs for the prevention of offenses;
- develop, approve and implement programs for the prevention of offenses;
- studies the criminogenic situation in the country, individual regions, districts and cities, analyzes the effectiveness of using existing forces and means to prevent and eliminate offenses;
- carry out the prevention of offenses, including identifying and eliminating the causes of the commission of offenses and the conditions that make them possible;
- keeps records of violations, persons who committed them and victims of violations, conducts an analysis of these data;
- Carries out preventive registration of persons provided for in Article 35 of the Law;
- identifies individuals associated with banned organizations and religious extremist groups, and takes measures against them;
- ensures control over compliance with the passport-visa regime, the rules and procedure for the storage of civilian and service weapons and ammunition for them by citizens and legal entities;
- participate in the disclosure of crimes and the search for missing persons and persons who avoid appearing before the investigation, court;
- takes measures for social rehabilitation and social adaptation;
- interacts with other bodies and institutions that directly carry out and participate in the prevention of offenses.

It was established that internal affairs bodies may exercise other powers in accordance with the legislation.

The adoption of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Internal Affairs Bodies" on September 16, 2016, played a significant role in understanding the legal foundations of the activities of crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies, their structural organization and current state, as well as defining their goals and objectives. Specifically, Article 2 of the law stipulates that the main tasks of internal affairs bodies are to protect the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of citizens, property of individuals and legal entities, and the constitutional order; to ensure the rule of law and the security of individuals, society and the state; as well as to prevent offenses. Article 4 identifies crime prevention as one of the main directions of internal affairs bodies' activities, including identifying and eliminating the causes and conditions that enable offenses, and identifying persons prone to committing offenses.

Furthermore, Article 15 of the law specifically notes that the base stations of internal affairs bodies, which are one of the main structural units of crime prevention services, are the primary local units of district and city internal affairs departments. These base stations are organized to ensure cooperation between internal affairs bodies and the public, and directly

maintain public order in villages, auls and mahallas, ensure citizens' safety, prevent crime, and combat criminal activity.

Additionally, it was determined that the base stations of internal affairs bodies should carry out activities with a staff comprising senior crime prevention inspectors, inspectors, and their assistants for maintaining public order. Crime prevention inspectors are to be appointed by the decision of the district (city) Council of People's Deputies and are required to submit reports to citizens' self-government bodies in the prescribed manner. It was also established that other units of internal affairs bodies may be involved in organizing the work of these base stations.

It should be noted that today, the crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies are effectively working to maintain public order and ensure public safety in residential areas, organize crime prevention, raise the legal awareness and culture of the population, and create a lifestyle that fully corresponds to the way of life, spirituality, values, and mentality of our people. However, as society continually develops, offenses also evolve, becoming more complex and sophisticated. Therefore, the effective implementation of crime prevention and the fight against crime remains one of the pressing tasks of our time.

In conclusion, it can be said that raising the effectiveness and efficiency of crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies to a new level is a requirement of today. Based on this requirement, it is advisable for law enforcement agencies to carry out crime prevention services to maintain public order and ensure public safety, implement crime prevention, and eliminate the causes and conditions that contribute to the commission of offenses. This should be done based on laws and regulatory legal acts, effectively using various forms and methods of activity, as well as official powers.

At the same time, in the 21st century, with the rapid development of modern information and communication technologies and the widespread prevalence of modern threats in global social life, the types of offenses are increasingly developing, becoming more complex and sophisticated as our society evolves. Correspondingly, it is axiomatic that the legal foundations of the activities of crime prevention services of internal affairs bodies, in other words, the laws and regulations governing their activities, should be improved in a unique way, keeping pace with the times. After all, the continuous implementation of measures aimed at preventing offenses, combating crime, protecting the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of individuals, maintaining public order and ensuring public safety, identifying and eliminating the causes of offenses and the conditions that allow them to be committed is one of the main directions for the future of our country.

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